

A Quantitative Analysis of Key Factors Influencing Reading Skill Acquisition Among Teacher Education Students at Sulu State College

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Abstract

Reading skills form the foundation of academic learning and are essential for communication, critical thinking and lifelong education. This descriptive-correlational study investigates the various determinants that impact the development of reading skill among teacher education students at Sulu State College. While t-test for independent samples determined the significant differences as to the Gender, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) determined the significant differences when data were grouped according to age, year level and parent educational attainment. Frequency counts and percentages determined the respondent's profile; mean and standard deviation determined the extent of subsumed categories, such as Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and

Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor. A moderate correlation was found between the key factors influencing the reading skill acquisition in the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). As a result, the need for enhanced reading programs, targeted instructional strategies, and supportive learning environments to strengthen the reading competencies of future educators at Sulu State College became crucial. The result of this study tends to support the Caldoza (2022) study on Factors Affecting Reading Comprehension Among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies of Students (Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor).

Keywords: *Reading Skill Acquisition, Teacher Education Students, Sulu State College*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a foundational skill that serves as a gateway to academic achievement and lifelong learning. In the context of basic education, the development of reading skills during the intermediate years is especially critical, as it marks the transition from learning to read to reading to learn. However, many learners in various regions of the Philippines, including Sulu, continue to struggle with acquiring essential reading skills. This persistent literacy gap underscores the urgency of identifying and addressing the key factors that influence reading development among school-aged children.

As Claessen et al. (2020) defined, reading difficulties are present in the world. The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) results from PISA 2018 revealed that reading is among the areas

that fifteen-year-old students in the Philippines scored lower than those in majority of the countries and economies that participated in PISA 2018. The country's average reading score was 340 score points, on a par with that of the Dominican Republic. That is, 80% of the Filipino students did not reach the minimum level of proficiency in reading. Their poor score in English, Mathematics and Science are attributed to the students' lack of ability in basic reading and comprehension. One of the priorities of the Department is Literacy improvement.

Improving all students' reading skills in order to narrow the reading achievement gap is one of the essential goals of the No Child Left Behind Act (NCLB) and Every Student Succeed Act (ESSA). Closing the gap can be done through requiring and encouraging schools to integrate high standards, high quality instruction, and teaching with research-based material and assessments (International Literacy Association 2016).

In Sulu State College, educators face a unique set of challenges in fostering literacy due to socio-economic disparities, resource limitations, and diverse learner backgrounds. While interventions have been introduced to improve literacy outcomes, there remains a pressing need for evidence-based insights that can guide more targeted and effective approaches to reading instruction.

Objectives of the study

The study's primary goal is to investigate the various factors influencing the acquisition of reading skills among teacher education students. Specifically, it examines the influence of individual background knowledge, individual attitude and motivation, teacher factors, and school factors on reading proficiency. By analyzing these variables, the study seeks to provide empirical data that can inform local educational policies, instructional strategies, and resource allocation efforts aimed at improving literacy outcomes in the region.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design method was used in this study. In the School of Teacher Education at Sulu State College, 120 representative samples were randomly selected from first to fourth year level. This will guarantee that each respondent has an equal probability of being included. The President of Sulu State College, the Dean of School of Teacher Education and the teachers were asked permission to administer the questionnaire and conduct the retrieval. Frequency counts and percentages were employed, mean and standards deviation determined the extent of the factors encompassed within the context of Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor; t-test for independent samples determined the significant differences as to the gender, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) determined the significant differences; and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (Pearson r) determined moderate positive correlations. The significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the acquisition of reading skills among teacher education students at Sulu State College.

The Caldoza (2022) research instrument was used on the Factors Affecting Reading Comprehension Among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies of Students that encompasses domains as such Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor. There are two sections to the research tool. The first section of the questionnaire sought for the information on the gender, age, year level and parent educational attainment. In Part II, information was gathered on the degree to which Individual Background knowledge (10 items), Individual Attitude and Motivation (5 items), Teacher Factor (10 items), and School Factor (5 items) influenced the respondents reading skill acquisition. The 5-point modified Likert Scale which has the values 5=Strongly Agree (SA), 4=Agree (A), 3=uncertain

(U), 2= Disagree (D), 1= Strongly Disagree (SD) was used to analyze the data received from this questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The demographic profile of 120 teacher education respondents shows that there are more female respondents than male respondents. More than half of the majority respondents fall into 17-19 age range and are predominated in number by female gender. They are equally represented in terms of year Level and more than half of them whose parent's educational attainment were elementary as the highest level of schooling.

3.1 Factors influencing the reading skill acquisition of teacher education students at Sulu State College

Individual Background knowledge

Respondents expressed agreement that they possessed high extent of individual background knowledge, as evidenced by the total weighted mean score of 3.8874 with standard deviation of .57705 which is rated as "Agree". They understand that problems with learning difficulties experienced by students can adopt inappropriate use of background knowledge and that they believed their individual background knowledge greatly influenced reading proficiency.

Individual Attitude and Motivation

A total weighted mean score of 4.1233 with a standard deviation of .61246 and a rating of "Agree" shows that respondents believed that individual attitude and motivation matters in improving acquisition of reading skills.

Teacher Factor

A total weighted mean score of 4.4550 with a standard deviation of .46807 and a rating as "Agree", shows that respondents thought that teachers in school of teacher education at Sulu State College exhibit efficient pedagogical knowledge and skills as such they are able to impart effective teaching in different subjects.

School Factor

Respondents who received an overall weighted mean score of 4.0950 with a standard deviation of .52562 and were asked to rate their agreement with the statement "Agree" expressed that Sulu State College is adequately providing instructional materials and support to ensure effective learning among teacher education students.

According to gender

When data are grouped according to gender, all the sub-categories subsumed on the extent of factors influencing the acquisition of the reading skills with their corresponding Mean Differences, t-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, male and female student-respondents in this study although vary in their gender; however, they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors influencing the acquisition of the reading skills. This result implies that being a male student-respondent this may not make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors influencing the acquisition of the reading skills over female respondents, or vice versa.

Therefore, the claim which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of factors influencing the acquisition of the reading skills of teacher education students when data are grouped according to gender” is accepted.

According to age

Out of 120 student-respondents, 28 (23.3%) are 16-17 years old, and 64 (53.3%) are 18-19 years old, and 28 (23.3%) are 20 years old & above. This result reveals that more than one-half or majority of the total respondents involved are within 17-19 years old.

According to Year level

Student-respondents result implies, 40 (33.3%) are 1st year level, 40 (33.3%) are 2nd year, and 40 (33.3%) are 3rd year level. This result implies that pupil-respondents involved in this study are equally represented in terms of year Level.

According to Parent’s educational attainment

Results revealed 90 (75.0%) are whose parents have elementary level, 24 (20.0%) are whose parents have secondary level, and 67 (5.0%) are whose parents have tertiary level of education. This implies that student-respondents involved in this study are whose parent’s educational attainment is elementary level.

The degree of correlations specifically demonstrates:

- 1) Moderate positive correlation between Individual Background knowledge and Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor.
- 2) Low positive correlation between Individual Attitude and Motivation and Teacher Factor, and School Factor; and
- 3) Moderate positive correlation between Motivation and Teacher Factor and School Factor.

These findings show generally, the categories subsumed the extent of acquisition of reading skills among teacher education students are moderately correlated. Therefore, the claim that, “There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the acquisition of reading skills among teacher education students”, is therefore rejected.

CONCLUSION

This descriptive-correlational study investigates the various determinants that impact the development of reading skill among teacher education students at Sulu State College. In terms of gender, age, year level and parent’s educational attainment, teacher education respondents are fairly represented. On the average, student-respondents expressed agreement that their reading skills are positively influenced by their Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factors, and School Factors. Generally, profile variables like age, gender, year level, and parent’s educational attainment do not intervene in ways how student-respondents assess the extent of the factors influencing the acquisition of the reading skills among teacher education students at SSC-Sulu. The group of student respondents who generally rated the extent of acquisition of reading skills among teacher education students in terms of Individual Background knowledge as “Agree” may possibly the same group of student-respondents who rated the extent of Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factors, and School Factors as “Agree”, respectively. This study tends to support the Caldoza (2022) study on Factors Affecting Reading Comprehension Among

Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies of Students (Individual Background knowledge, Individual Attitude and Motivation, Teacher Factor, and School Factor).

Recommendations

This study suggests that administrators should continue to facilitate the provision of efficient learning environment with sufficient instructional facilities including up-to-date reading materials; Dean of Different schools at Sulu State College -Sulu should strengthen reading instruction programs to promote positive attitudes and motivation towards reading; teachers should be provided more with professional trainings that would enhance their pedagogical knowledge and skills in teaching with proper application of reading approaches; policy integration and institutional support should always be evident. Furthermore, they advise future

researchers to conduct studies akin to this considering other variables such as efficacy of teachers' use of ICT materials, learning strategies and morale of school of education teachers at Sulu State College.

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